

Motion-Aware LiDAR Correction

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Abstract—LiDAR scans often suffer from skewing artifacts when the sensor moves during acquisition, degrading the quality of mapping and localization in robotics applications. We propose a novel method to correct this distortion by estimating the sensor’s velocities during the scan acquisition using a customized Iterative Closest Point algorithm. Our approach integrates temporal interpolation and a modified KD-tree structure to efficiently handle real-time applications. The effectiveness of the proposed system is demonstrated in the experiments using real-world datasets, significantly improving the accuracy of the scan.

Index Terms—Robotics, Lidar, Mapping

Due to their high accuracy and robustness, mechanical Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR)s are a fundamental component in various robotic applications, such as obstacle avoidance and Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM). However, considering that full scan acquisition is not instantaneous, mechanical LiDAR scans suffer from the skewing effect when the sensor moves during data acquisition, reducing the quality of the measurements. In this work, we propose a method to correct motion distortion (deskewing) in LiDAR measurements, where we customize an Iterative Closest Point (ICP) paradigm by utilizing the normal vectors of planar patches and the endpoints timestamp to estimate the sensor’s velocities intra-scan. Extending our previous work in [4], knowing the velocity of the sensor when each endpoint was acquired, we will be able to remove the distortion from the measurements, as seen in Fig. 1. To enhance performance for real-time applications, we exploit a variant of the KD-tree data structure, which enables the partitioning of the space, allowing for precise temporal interpolation of LiDAR scans.

I. PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. ICP

As reported in our previous work [4] to solve the problem of deskewing, we parametrize endpoints as a function of velocity and time. Let \mathbf{p}_{t_j} be a laser endpoint at time t_j , and \mathbf{n}_{t_j} the approximated surface normal at the same point, both expressed in the laser frame. With $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{v} \ \boldsymbol{\omega})^T$ we denote the linear and angular velocities, while $\mathbf{T}_j \in \mathbb{SE}(3)$ is the location of the sensor w.r.t. the world frame at the beginning of the scan t_j^s . The position of the endpoint in the world frame can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{p}_j = \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{v}_j, \boldsymbol{\omega}_j, t_j) \simeq \mathbf{T}_j[\exp(\boldsymbol{\omega}_j \Delta t_j) | \mathbf{v}_j \Delta t_j] \mathbf{p}_{t_j}. \quad (1)$$

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Fig. 1. (a) is the initial LiDAR measurements, while (b) shows the correspondences between the initial scan, and the corrected one after estimating the velocities and transforming the tree, and Finally, (c) is the output of our proposed system

Here $\exp(\boldsymbol{\omega}_j \Delta t_j)$ is an operator that computes a rotation matrix by integrating the velocity in the interval $\Delta t_j = t_j - t_j^s$, while $\mathbf{v}_j \Delta t_j$ is the displacement in translation. Similarly, we can map the normal vector in the world frame as follows:

$$\mathbf{n}_j = \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{v}_j, \boldsymbol{\omega}_j, t_j) \simeq \mathbf{R}_j[\exp(\boldsymbol{\omega}_j \Delta t_j)] \mathbf{n}_{t_j}. \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{R}_j is the rotation matrix in \mathbf{T}_j .

Assuming to know that two endpoints at t_i and at t_j refer to the same portion of the environment we introduce a symmetric *point-to-plane* metric as a function of the velocities as follows:

$$\mathbf{e}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j, t_i, t_j) = (\mathbf{p}_j - \mathbf{p}_i)^T \cdot \mathbf{n}_i \quad (3)$$

$\mathbf{e}(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j, t_i, t_j) \in \mathbb{R}^1$, where it accounts for the distance between the two corresponding points projected along the normal vector.

The cost function is a quadratic expression in the form

$$(\mathcal{X}) = \sum_{\{(t_i, t_j)\}} \rho(\|\mathbf{e}(\mathbf{x}, t_i, t_j)\|^2), \quad (4)$$

where $\rho(\cdot)$ is a Huber cost function to reduce the effect of outliers, and $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_{1:N}\}$ are *all* intra scan velocities.

Our system carries on the estimation of the velocities in an iterative manner. At each step, it first determines the correspondences $\{(t_i, t_j)\}$ by the nearest neighbor criterion using the deskewed clouds based on the previous estimate. Subsequently it minimizes Eq. (4) w.r.t the velocities \mathcal{X} , using Iterative Reweighted Least Squares [3].

The time required by the minimization is not a concern, however, the search for correspondence is, since it has to be carried on for each measurement of each scan in the estimation. Hence, we organize the data acquired within a scan in a variant of KD-Tree that uses PCA to recursively partition the endpoints along the direction of maximum variation, according to the procedure outlined in our previous work [2]. Let $N_k = \langle \boldsymbol{\mu}_k, \mathbf{d}_k, \mathbf{n}_k, N_{l(k)}, N_{r(k)} \rangle$ be a generic node in the tree. Here $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$, is the mean of the endpoints, $\mathbf{d}_k \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the direction of maximum spread, and \mathbf{n}_k is the direction of minimum spread that encodes the surface's normal. $N_{l(k)}$ and $N_{r(k)}$ are the left and right children nodes respectively. A search of a query point \mathbf{q} starts from the root, and proceeds by selecting the left or the right child according to the following predicate:

$$(\mathbf{q} - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k) \cdot \mathbf{d}_k > 0. \quad (5)$$

Whereas using such a structure significantly improves the search, the construction of the KD-Tree might take time. Since in our system we need to deskew the clouds at each iteration, reconstructing the tree would negatively impact the performance. Hence, in the remainder of this paper we present a strategy that:

- allows to quickly modify a kd-tree to incorporate the effects of the deskewing, in a time proportional to the number of nodes (and not of points).
- carries on the optimization on the leaves of the kd-tree, instead that on the single endpoints, hence reducing the computation

B. KD-Tree with temporal information

Since each measurement point \mathbf{p}_k has its own timestamp t_k , we can directly encode this information in the nodes by adding one more field τ_k that represents the average of the timestamps of the points falling in the space partition defined by the node. Hence, in our tree a node will be $N_k = \langle \boldsymbol{\mu}_k, \mathbf{d}_k, \mathbf{n}_k, \tau_k, N_{l(k)}, N_{r(k)} \rangle$. To remove skewing from a tree, we directly use Eq. (1) on the mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and Eq. (2) on normal \mathbf{n} and direction \mathbf{d} , where the error function becomes:

$$\mathbf{e}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_k, \boldsymbol{\mu}_v, t_k, t_v) = (\mathbf{T}_v \boldsymbol{\mu}_v - \mathbf{T}_k \boldsymbol{\mu}_k) \cdot (\mathbf{R}_k \mathbf{n}_k). \quad (6)$$

As integration time $\Delta = \tau - t^s$ we use the difference between the average timestamp stored in the node and the start of the scan.

II. EXPERIMENT

We validated our system by applying it to refine the output of an internal SLAM pipeline, which does not handle the skewing effects. Our system operates as a post-processing step on an existing map, aiming to estimate intra-scan velocities. The SLAM system produces a set of transformations T_i and corresponding scans S_i , which we treat as keyframes $\langle T_i, S_i \rangle$.

The batch refinement procedure is iterative and performs the following steps:

- calculation of co-visibility graph between keyframes

Fig. 2. The circle in the map represents a wall where (a) is the initial LiDAR measurements, while (b) shows the same part of the map after 4 iterations, and Finally, (c) is the output of our proposed system after 10 iterations

- refinement of the poses $\{T_i\}$ by using multi-view ICP
- seek for correspondences based on the actual kd-trees
- solution of the optimization problem in Eq. (4).
- computation of the new kd-trees based on the procedure outlined in Sec. I-B.

Using the VBR public dataset [1], Fig. 2, we observed significant improvement in the map quality after applying our method. The Absolute Trajectory Error (ATE) was reduced from 0.279 meters to 0.220 meters on a 1.6 km dataset. Initially, multi-view ICP was used to jointly optimize structure and trajectory. Our method then estimated velocities between corresponding keyframe nodes, transforming the KD-tree's mean and normal vectors as described in Sec. I-A. Finally, we re-applied multi-view ICP to further optimize the transformed point clouds.

III. CONCLUSION

In this abstract, we presented our method for compensating the effect of the LiDAR motion that relies on an effective search structure, that can be transformed between the iterations with minimal computational effort. Additionally, we tested the method on real data by assembling a working system. Our software iteratively refines the map by sequentially refining the trajectory with multi-view ICP and deskewing the scans based on the estimated velocities. Future work will focus on deeper analysis and on the simultaneous optimization of trajectory and velocities.

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